

The law of constancy of the velocity of light *in vacuo*, which constitutes one of the fundamental assumptions in the special theory of relativity and to which we have already frequently referred, cannot claim an unlimited validity.

Albert Einstein (1920)

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Varying speed of light in the conformal cosmology

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ABSTRACT

In modelling the cosmic expansion, the conformal cosmology (CC) has several advantages over the standard cosmological model based on the FLRW metric: it is Lorentz invariant, it leaves the Maxwell's equations unchanged from their form in the Minkowski spacetime, it properly predicts the cosmological redshift and cosmic time dilation, and it fits the Type Ia supernova luminosity data without introducing dark energy into cosmological equations. However, the CC metric seems controversial because it predicts a varying speed of light with cosmic time. Here, we show that this controversy is apparent, because the measured physical speed of light is always coordinate-dependent being not referred to an inertial free-falling system but to a non-inertial system experiencing the gravity field. Hence, the CC universe is fully consistent with the general relativity theory and physically well justified. Since the universe is dynamic and evolves in time, the space curvature is time dependent and the speed of light should vary. Importantly, the photons redshifted due to the expansion conserve their energy in the CC universe. The frequency of photons decreases due to the redshift, but their speed increases with the scale factor $a(t)$. Hence, both effects are compensated and the photon energy is conserved.

1. INTRODUCTION

The speed of light c in vacuum is believed to be a universal nature constant being the fundamental pillar of special and general relativity and modern physics (Uzan 2003). Although theories of the varying speed of light (VSL) have been proposed (Moffat 1993; Albrecht & Magueijo 1999; Barrow 1999; Magueijo 2003, 2009; Moffat 2016), they are not paid much attention, because they are expected to be inconsistent with general relativity (GR) and to cause essential damage to current physics. Nevertheless, even such outstanding physicists as Dicke (1957) or Dirac (1938, 1979) argue that the varying speed of light is physically admissible and the physical laws may be changing and nature constants may be varying with cosmological time.

So far, several alternative VSL theories have been proposed (Magueijo 2003). For example, Moffat (1993) introduced an idea of spontaneous breaking of local Lorentz invariance associated with a large increase of the light speed in the early Universe to keep causality and solve the horizon problem. Similarly, Albrecht &

Magueijo (1999) postulated breaking Lorentz invariance (and consequently non-conservation of energy) associated with a high light speed in the early Universe. They showed that their scenario could solve horizon, flatness and cosmological constant problems. Clayton & Moffat (1999) proposed the so-called bimetric VSL theory by introducing two metrics: one for gravity and one for matter. In this theory, the speed of light is varying and differs from the speed of gravitational waves. The VSL is also produced if the dispersion relation of photons is deformed (Ellis et al. 2000) or it appears in the brane-world scenario (Kiritsis 1999).

In recent years, there have been also efforts to test the VSL theories by cosmological observations. For example, Qi et al. (2014) considered dark energy and dark matter in their cosmological model and the speed of light in the form $c(t) = c_0 a^n(t)$, where c_0 is the current value of the speed of light and n is a constant. They tested the model through combined observations of the Type Ia supernovae, baryon acoustic oscillations, $H(z)$ and the cosmic microwave background, and found that the speed of light should be constant with high significance.

By contrast, [Salzano & Dabrowski \(2017\)](#) found that VSL scenarios might fit cosmological data better than the Λ CDM model. Nevertheless, the dark energy contribution is still needed in the VSL models in their tests. A different approach in setting limits on variation in c was proposed by [Eaves \(2021\)](#), based on constraints on variation in the gravitational constant G . Using observations in the Solar system, he concluded that the variation in c should be negligible ($|n| < 0.008$). Another precise measurements of c applicable in future was presented by [Cao et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Cao et al. \(2020\)](#), who proposed exploiting strong gravitational lensing with Type Ia supernovae or quasars as background sources.

It should be noted, however, that the idea of the varying speed of light does not mean necessarily a violation of GR proposed by the above mentioned VSL theories. According to [Einstein \(1920\)](#): ‘*the law of constancy of the velocity of light in vacuo, which constitutes one of the fundamental assumptions in the special theory of relativity and to which we have already frequently referred, cannot claim an unlimited validity its results hold only so long as we are able to disregard the influences of gravitational fields on the phenomena (e.g. of light)*’. Hence, there are also solutions characterized by the varying speed of light being fully consistent with GR. A typical example of the varying speed of light treated in GR is the gravitational lensing, since ‘*A curvature of rays of light can only take place when the velocity of propagation of light varies with position*’ ([Einstein 1920](#)).

The reason for varying c in GR solutions is clear. The speed of light is always gauged in some fixed coordinate system by using the standard clock (e.g., atomic clock) for measuring time and a rigid rod for measuring distances. Hence, we mean by c the proper (physical) coordinate-dependent speed of light, which is usually not referred to an inertial free-falling system but to a non-inertial system experiencing the gravity field. This applies, e.g., to observers in rest in the gravitational field described by the Schwarzschild metric or to observers in rest in a homogeneous, isotropic, curved universe described by the conformal cosmology (CC) metric ([Hawking & Ellis 1973](#); [Endean 1994, 1997](#); [Kastrup 2008](#)). While the gravity field is spatially dependent in the Schwarzschild metric, it depends on time due to the evolution of the Universe in the CC metric. In both cases, the space is distorted and time is dilated. This leads to variation in c with the space or time coordinates when measured in these metrics.

Whether the speed of light is constant or not in any GR solution, depends on the form of the time-time component g_{00} of the metric tensor $g_{\alpha\beta}$. If g_{00} is fixed as in the FLRW metric commonly used for describing the ex-

panding universe, the comoving and proper times equal and the speed of light is constant. In this case, the rate of the cosmic time is uniform and no time dilation for observers in rest can appear during the evolution of the Universe. If g_{00} is a function of space or time coordinates, the comoving and proper times differ and the proper coordinate-dependent speed of light is varying. If c depends only on time as in the CC metric, such a GR solution will look apparently as being of the VSL type (violating GR).

In this paper, we focus on analysing the effect of the varying proper coordinate speed of light associated with the CC metric ([Endean 1994, 1997](#); [Barut et al. 1994](#); [Dabrowski et al. 2009](#); [Mannheim 1990, 2006, 2012](#)). This metric is attractive for cosmology for several reasons: (1) it is Lorentz invariant, (2) it leaves the Maxwell’s equations unchanged from their form in the Minkowski spacetime, (3) it is developed within the Einstein’s field equations, and (4) it obeys the energy conservation law. These exceptional properties predestine the CC metric to be widely used in new cosmological models. Moreover, [Behnke et al. \(2002\)](#) and [Vavryčuk \(2022\)](#) showed that this metric is actually supported by Type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) observations. While the FLRW metric produces essential discrepancy with the SNe Ia data, which can only be removed by introducing dark energy, the CC metric fits the SNe Ia data with no need to consider dark energy.

Despite the progress in understanding properties of the CC metric, its fundamental role in describing the cosmic expansion is still not fully recognized. Here we focus on the apparently controversial aspect of the CC metric associated with the varying speed of light. We study this unexpected and overlooked property of the CC metric in detail. We clarify confusions about the comoving and proper times, and derive the comoving and proper speeds of photons in the CC metric. Finally, we find how the energy of photons is evolved in time, and discuss the energy conservation law for photons in this metric.

2. THEORY

2.1. FLRW and CC metrics

Let us assume a homogeneous and isotropic universe described by the FLRW metric ([Peacock 1999](#))

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + a^2(t) \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right), \quad (1)$$

and by the CC metric ([Grøn & Johannesen 2011](#); [Vavryčuk 2022](#))

$$ds^2 = a^2(t) \left(-c^2 dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right), \quad (2)$$

where $a(t)$ is the scale factor defining the universe expansion, t is the comoving time, c is the proper speed of light at present, k is the Gaussian curvature of the space, r is the comoving distance, and Ω is the solid angle.

To avoid confusions, we have to emphasize the following facts:

- A common opinion that Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) are physically equivalent, because they can be transformed one to the other by rescaling time, is wrong. Obviously, the Einstein equations are coordinate invariant, but it does not mean that we can rescale coordinates with no physical consequences.
- Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) describe metrics of two essentially different physical systems. While the component of the metric tensor g_{00} is time independent in Eq. (1), it depends on time in Eq. (2). Hence, Eq. (2) encompasses the space expansion as well as the time dilation during the evolution of the Universe
- Eq. (1) predicts the comoving and proper time to be identical. Eq. (2) predicts the comoving and proper time to be different.
- Eq. (2) is not a metric for a static universe expressed in rescaled units. Such argument is wrong because, the static universe with an invariant rate of time is physically different from an expanding universe with a varying rate of time.

Note that the time dependence of the metric tensor g_{00} assumed in the CC metric is supported by observations of light curves of Type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia). Since the SNe Ia display rather uniform light curves, they can serve as the standard candles as well as the standard local clocks. The spectral evolution of the light curves and stretching of time in the observer frame was disclosed by many authors (Leibundgut et al. 1996; Goldhaber et al. 1997, 2001; Phillips et al. 1999). The stretching of light curves at high redshift is firmly acknowledged and corrections for time dilation are now routinely applied to the SNe Ia data (Leibundgut 2001; Goobar & Leibundgut 2011). The light curve stretching is commonly interpreted as the effect of the cosmic time dilation even though the standard model based on the FLRW metric defined in Eq. (1) does not allow it.

2.2. Comoving and proper speeds of photons

The essential difference between the FLRW and CC metrics is convincingly demonstrated on the comoving

and proper speeds of photons in both models. The propagation of photons is described by the equation of the null geodesics, $ds^2 = 0$. For the FLRW metric, we get

$$c^2 dt^2 = a^2(t) dl^2, \quad dl^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2. \quad (3)$$

Hence, the comoving (i.e., contravariant) speed of light \hat{c} is

$$\hat{c} = \frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{c}{a(t)}, \quad (4)$$

and the proper speed of light C is

$$C = \sqrt{g_{ii}} \hat{c} = a(t) \hat{c} = c. \quad (5)$$

For the CC metric, we get

$$a^2(t) (-c^2 dt^2 + dl^2) = 0. \quad (6)$$

Hence, the comoving (i.e., contravariant) speed of light \hat{c} is

$$\hat{c} = \frac{dl}{dt} = c, \quad (7)$$

and the proper speed of light C is

$$C = \sqrt{g_{ii}} \hat{c} = a(t) \hat{c} = a(t)c. \quad (8)$$

Eqs (4-5) and Eqs (7-8) show that both the FLRW and CC metrics are physically different. While the comoving speed of light varies with time, $\hat{c} = c/a(t)$, in the FLRW metric, it is constant in the CC metric. The property of the constant comoving speed of light in the CC metric is emphasized, e.g., by Infeld & Schild (1945) and Grøn & Johannesen (2011). By contrast, the proper (physical) speed of light is constant, $C = c$, in the FLRW metric, but it varies with time, $C = a(t)c$, in the CC metric. Hence, the CC metric resembles the VSL cosmologies in this point.

2.3. Varying speed of light in GR

The concept of the varying speed of light treated in this paper seems apparently to be against the basic principles of the GR theory. This is incorrect, because we do not study the speed of light in free-falling inertial coordinate systems, but in non-inertial systems. In contrast to the free-falling systems, the non-inertial systems are not equivalent, because the acceleration due to gravity is not cancelled with the gravitational field. Hence, the varying proper coordinate-dependent speed of light in the conformal cosmology is fully consistent with GR being analogous, for example, to the varying (coordinate) speed of light known in the famous Schwarzschild solution.

The Schwarzschild metric in the standard coordinates is defined as follows

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (9)$$

where $r_s = 2GM/c^2$ is the Schwarzschild radius, G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the body, r and t are the coordinate (contravariant) distance and time. Velocity c is the speed of light far from the source of gravity. Equation for the light ray obeys the null geodesics, $ds = 0$, hence we get for a radial ray, $d\Omega = 0$,

$$\hat{c} = \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) c, \quad (10)$$

where \hat{c} is the contravariant component of the radial velocity of light. The physical component of the light speed C is

$$C = \sqrt{g_{rr}} \hat{c} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} c. \quad (11)$$

Quantity C is the proper (physical) speed of light for a radial ray measured in the coordinate system of an observer with a fixed position with respect to the source of gravity. This system is non-inertial, because it experiences the gravity field of the central mass. In this system, the proper speed of light C goes to zero for $r \rightarrow r_s$. Obviously, it does not imply any contradiction with the GR theory.

Note that Eqs (9-11) are notoriously known in GR. We present them here to emphasize that the concept of the VSL in the CC metric is fully analogous to the Schwarzschild metric. The only difference is that the speed of light is spatially dependent in the Schwarzschild metric but it is time dependent in the CC metric.

Using the CC metric for the expanding universe has also another advantage. In this case, the cosmological and the gravitational redshifts are defined by the same formula

$$1 + z = \sqrt{\frac{g_{00}(r)}{g_{00}(e)}}, \quad (12)$$

where $g_{00}(e)$ and $g_{00}(r)$ are the time components of the metric tensor $g_{\alpha\beta}$ for the emitter and receiver, respectively. Hence, the gravitational and cosmological redshifts are physically the same phenomena. The only difference is, that the gravitational redshift is produced by a local gravitational field of a massive body, while the cosmological redshift is produced by a global gravitational field of the whole Universe.

2.4. Energy of photons

Obviously, the variable speed of light in the CC metric might have consequences for energy of photons in the expanding universe. In general relativity, the behaviour of energy and momentum of particles is described by the stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$, which is expressed for the photon fluid as follows

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{c^2} (u + P) U^\mu U^\nu + P g^{\mu\nu}, \quad (13)$$

where $u = nE$ is the energy density of the photon fluid, n is the number density of photons, E is the energy of individual photons, P is the pressure, U^μ is the 4-velocity, and $g^{\mu\nu}$ the metric tensor. The tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ satisfies the following equation

$$T^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} = 0, \quad (14)$$

which expresses the conservation law of energy and momentum. In both the FLRW and CC metrics, tensor $T^\mu{}_\nu = T^{\mu\alpha} g_{\alpha\nu}$ reads

$$T^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} -u & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & P \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Since the universe is unbounded, the total energy of the photon fluid cannot escape through a boundary and thus it must be conserved. We assume a system of photons, which do not interact with themselves or with other matter. Since photons travel freely in an unbounded space, they spend no work when the space is expanding or contracting. Consequently, the photon fluid behaves as pressureless, $P = 0$, and tensor $T^\mu{}_\nu$ simplifies to $T^\mu{}_\nu = \text{diag}[-u, 0, 0, 0]$.

Note that the concept of the pressureless photon fluid looks strange and against the common opinion that the radiation field produces a non-zero pressure $P = 1/3u$. However, this equation is valid for an electromagnetic field captured in a closed volume bounded by ideally reflecting walls. The pressure in this field originates in the reflection of photons on the walls. If the walls are moving and the volume is increased, the photons spend work, when interacting with the walls. Consequently, the energy density and the pressure decrease. By contrast, no radiation pressure can be maintained in the open space with no boundaries and no work is spent by photons when the space is increased. This implies that photons in the empty expanding universe form the pressureless photon fluid.

Inserting $\mu = 0$ into Eq. (14), we get the energy conservation law,

$$T^{0\nu}{}_{;\nu} = 0, \quad (16)$$

expressed as

$$3\dot{a}u + \dot{u}a = 0, \quad (17)$$

and consequently

$$\frac{d}{dt} (ua^3) = 0. \quad (18)$$

Hence, the energy density u decreases with the increasing scale factor a as $u = u_0 a^{-3}$, where $u_0 = n_0 E_0$ is

the energy density at present ($a = 1$), n_0 is the number density of photons at present, and E_0 is the energy of individual photons at present. Since the number density of photons n decreases with a as $n = n_0 a^{-3}$, we get for the photon energy E in the past

$$E = E_0. \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) expresses the conservation of energy of individual photons during the expansion of the Universe. The equation applies to the FLRW metric as well as the CC metric. Expressing energy E_0 as

$$E_0 = p_0 c, \quad (20)$$

where c is the proper speed of light at present, $p_0 = \hat{h}\nu_0$ is the magnitude of the photon momentum at present, $\hat{h} = h/c$ is the Planck constant normalized by c , and ν_0 is the photon frequency. Analogously, we can write for energy E of a photon in the past

$$E = pC, \quad (21)$$

where $p = \hat{h}\nu$ and C are the momentum and proper speed of a photon in the past. Inserting Eqs (20) and (21) into Eq. (19), we get for the photon momentum p

$$p = p_0 \frac{c}{C}, \quad (22)$$

and for the photon frequency ν

$$\nu = \nu_0 \frac{c}{C}. \quad (23)$$

Using Eq. (5), we get for the FLRW metric

$$\nu = \nu_0. \quad (24)$$

Similarly, using Eq. (8), we get for the CC metric

$$\nu = \nu_0 a^{-1}. \quad (25)$$

Hence, the energy conservation law for photons implies that the frequency of photons is not changing in the FLRW metric. The same results was obtained by Vavryčuk (2022) using an independent approach. By contrast, the frequency of photons is redshifted in the CC metric. Still, the energy of photons is conserved, because the decrease of the photon frequency ν is compensated by the increase of the proper light speed C :

$$E = \hat{h}\nu C = \hat{h}\nu_0 a^{-1} ca = E_0. \quad (26)$$

Conservation of energy of photons described by Eq. (26) is expected from the physical point of view being a direct consequence of Eq. (16). This confirms that the

form of the stress-energy tensor for the photon fluid was correctly chosen.

Note that the inconsistency of the FLRW metric with redshift observations is evident also from the energy point of view. If we assume the constant speed of light as in the FLRW metric and photons redshifting during the space expansion, the energy of photons must decrease. This obviously violates the energy conservation law defined by Eq. (16).

3. DISCUSSION

It is commonly assumed that we can keep the time component g_{00} of the metric tensor constant in the model of the expanding universe, because we have a freedom of choosing time. However, the argument that the time coordinate can be rescaled with no physical consequences is misleading. Applying the same argument to the space coordinates, we could argue that we do not need to introduce the space expansion. We could claim that the expanding and static universes are physically equivalent, because the space coordinates are just rescaled and GR is coordinate invariant. This is evidently wrong, because rescaling time or space coordinates in the pure mathematical sense does not resolve the physical problem whether the cosmic time is dilated (or not) and the cosmic space is distorted (or not) during the evolution of the Universe.

If we apply the CC metric, we have to strictly distinguish between the comoving and proper times similarly as we distinguish between the comoving and proper distances in the FLRW metric. The CC metric is more natural than the FLRW metric, because it treats time and space in a similar way. There is no reason to assume that space is expanded but time is not dilated during the cosmic evolution. Moreover, a detailed analysis of Vavryčuk (2022) reveals that the assumption of the invariant time in the FLRW metric is actually inconsistent with observations, because it predicts no cosmological redshift. Here, we arrived at the same conclusion in a completely different way. This finding is rather surprising but physically clear: if clocks connected to the photon do not change its rate with the cosmic time, the free non-interacting photon cannot change its frequency. Hence, the cosmological redshift is in fact a manifestation of the variation of g_{00} , similarly as for the gravitational redshift. In this sense, both the gravitational and cosmological redshifts are essentially the same phenomena, because they originate in varying g_{00} . The only difference is that g_{00} depends on spatial coordinates for the gravitational redshift but on the time coordinate for the cosmological redshift.

An inevitable consequence of the time dependence of g_{00} in the CC metric is a varying proper speed of light C in vacuum with cosmic time. It does not mean, however, that the GR theory is violated. According to Einstein (1920), the quantity c in the GR equations is referred to an inertial system unaffected by a gravitational field. However, the gravitational field cannot be avoided in cosmology, because it is produced by the Universe itself. Hence, the Cosmological Coordinate System is not inertial and gravity effects in this system vary in time. Since the Universe is not static but evolving with cosmic time, the proper (coordinate) speed of light C cannot be a nature constant independent of time. The mean mass density in the Universe is changing, and consequently the curvature of the Universe and properties of vacuum are changing. Since geometry of the Universe at high redshifts is different from that at present, there is no justification for assuming the proper (coordinate) speed of light independent of time. Therefore, a model of the dynamic universe must be associated with the varying speed of light with cosmic time.

In contrast to the FLRW metric, the CC metric is consistent with observations of the cosmological redshift. The conformal metric is attractive also for other reasons: it is Lorentz invariant and it leaves the Maxwell's equa-

tions unchanged. Moreover, the energy conservation law is valid even for the redshifted photons in this metric. The decrease of the energy due to the redshift is compensated by an increase of energy due to the increasing speed of light with the scale factor $a(t)$. This removes an obvious difficulty of the standard model: What happens with the energy of photons lost due to the redshift? How to explain an evident violation of the energy conservation law? In fact, this difficulty is apparent, because photons in the standard model keep their speed constant and they cannot be actually redshifted. Hence, no energy is lost. By contrast, photons in the conformal model are redshifted, but their speed increases with cosmic time. Again, no energy is lost. Consequently, photons can change their frequency and speed in the presence of the gravitational field, but the photon energy is conserved. The energy is not transmitted to or gained from the gravitational field.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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